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ASSESSMENT OF ESG INDICES OF PRESTIGIOUS HOTELS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the level of sustainability of prestigious hotels in Uzbekistan based on ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) indices. Within the framework of the study, InterContinental Tashkent, Wyndham Garden Zomin, and Silk Road Samarkand Eco Village were selected, and their environmental performance, social responsibility, and governance systems were compared. The results of the analysis show that large international hotels demonstrate leadership in governance and social criteria, while environmentally oriented complexes achieve higher results in terms of environmental sustainability. At the same time, the study identifies a lack of open ESG reporting, certification, and monitoring systems in most hotels. The findings substantiate the need for the systematic implementation of ESG principles in Uzbekistan's hotel industry and provide practical recommendations for the development of sustainable tourism.

Keywords: ESG indices, sustainable tourism, hotel industry, environmental sustainability, social responsibility, corporate governance, tourism of Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistondagi nufuzli mehmonxonalarning barqarorlik darajasi ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) indeksleri asosida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot doirasida InterContinental Tashkent, Wyndham Garden Zomin hamda Silk Road Samarkand Eco Village tanlab olinib, ularning ekologik samaradorligi, ijtimoiy mas'uliyati va boshqaruv tizimlari taqqoslandi. Tahlil natijalari yirik xalqaro mehmonxonalar boshqaruv va ijtimoiy mezonlar bo'yicha yetakchilik qilayotganini, ekologik yo'naltirilgan majmualar esa atrof-muhit barqarorligi jihatidan yuqori natijalarga erishayotganini ko'rsatdi. Shu bilan birga, ko'pgina mehmonxonalarda ochiq ESG hisobotlari, sertifikatlash va monitoring tizimlarining yetishmasligi aniqlandi. Olingan natijalar O'zbekiston mehmonxona sohasida ESG tamoyillarini tizimli joriy etish zaruratini asoslab beradi hamda barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalarni taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ESG indeksleri, barqaror turizm, mehmonxona sanoati, ekologik barqarorlik, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat, korporativ boshqaruv, O'zbekiston turizmi.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется уровень устойчивого развития престижных гостиниц Узбекистана на основе ESG-индексов (Environmental, Social, Governance). В рамках исследования были отобраны гостиницы InterContinental Tashkent, Wyndham Garden Zomin и Silk Road Samarkand Eco Village, по которым проведено сравнительное изучение экологической эффективности, социальной ответственности и систем корпоративного управления. Результаты анализа показывают, что крупные международные гостиницы демонстрируют лидерство по управленческим и социальным критериям, в то время как экологически ориентированные комплексы достигают более высоких показателей в сфере экологической устойчивости. Вместе с тем выявлена недостаточность открытой ESG-отчетности, сертификации и систем мониторинга в большинстве гостиниц. Полученные выводы обосновывают необходимость системного внедрения ESG-принципов в гостиничной индустрии Узбекистана и содержат практические рекомендации по развитию устойчивого туризма.

Ключевые слова: ESG-индексы, устойчивый туризм, гостиничная индустрия, экологическая устойчивость, социальная ответственность, корпоративное управление, туризм Узбекистана.

INTRODUCTION

ESG indices are international indicators that assess the level of sustainability of enterprises and organizations in environmental, social, and governance dimensions. Today, ESG requirements have become an important factor for hotels in increasing competitiveness in the tourism sector. Hotels in Uzbekistan are also striving to strengthen their image in the international market through these indices. Environmental criteria assess a hotel's energy efficiency, waste reduction, and the use of water-saving technologies. For example, installing solar panels, switching to LED lighting systems, and using recyclable materials contribute to higher evaluations. Social indicators are determined by employee training, improvement of working conditions, ensuring guest safety, and supporting local communities. In Uzbek hotels, sending employees to language courses or using

local products are good examples of such practices. Governance criteria include transparency, anti-corruption policies, and the presence of clear service quality standards. Achieving high scores in ESG indices increases the likelihood of hotels being chosen by international tourists. Moreover, environmentally friendly and socially responsible hotels are more attractive to investors. The sustainable development of Uzbekistan's tourism sector is closely linked to an increase in the number of hotels operating in accordance with ESG principles. Therefore, many hotels are beginning to incorporate sustainability policies into their strategies and to develop in line with international standards.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) framework has become a widely used tool for evaluating corporate sustainability, long-term performance, and stakeholder value creation, particularly in service-oriented industries such as hospitality. The conceptual foundation of ESG is rooted in the triple bottom line approach, which emphasizes the integration of economic, environmental, and social objectives within business strategies [3]. Empirical evidence consistently shows that strong ESG performance is positively associated with financial stability, risk reduction, and operational efficiency [4]. Eccles et al. [2] further demonstrate that firms with advanced sustainability practices exhibit superior organizational processes and governance quality, highlighting the strategic relevance of ESG integration. In the hospitality sector, sustainability practices play a crucial role in enhancing competitiveness, as environmentally and socially responsible hotels tend to attract more customers and investors [9]. Environmental initiatives such as energy efficiency, water-saving technologies, and climate-related strategies are closely linked to improved performance and resilience [1]. The social dimension of ESG, including employee training, working conditions, and service quality, is particularly important in hotels, where human capital directly influences customer satisfaction [9, 14]. Governance serves as the institutional foundation of ESG by ensuring transparency, accountability, and effective monitoring mechanisms [15]. Recent studies focusing on Uzbekistan indicate a growing emphasis on sustainable tourism and the need for institutional support and governance reforms to promote long-term development [7, 8]. However, systematic assessments of ESG indices in Uzbekistan's hotel sector remain limited, underscoring the relevance of the present study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative–comparative research design to assess the implementation of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) indices in prestigious hotels operating in Uzbekistan. The research is grounded in the ESG conceptual framework and the triple bottom line approach, which provide the theoretical basis for evaluating sustainability performance across environmental, social, and governance dimensions [3, 4]. Three hotels—InterContinental Tashkent, Wyndham Garden Zomin, and Silk Road Samarkand Eco Village—were purposefully selected due to their market prominence, differing operational models, and declared sustainability orientations, enabling a meaningful comparative analysis [7, 9]. Data were collected through secondary sources, including official hotel websites, publicly available corporate information, sustainability-related disclosures, and international guidelines on ESG and sustainable tourism [6, 15]. Environmental indicators focused on energy efficiency, resource optimization, and ecological impact, while social indicators assessed employee development, service quality, guest safety, and community engagement [1, 9]. Governance indicators examined transparency, data protection, management standards, and compliance with international best practices [2, 15]. The analysis was conducted using a descriptive scoring approach, allowing hotels to be compared across ESG dimensions on a standardized scale [4, 5]. This methodology enables the identification of strengths, weaknesses, and gaps in ESG implementation within Uzbekistan's hotel sector and provides a structured basis for practical recommendations aimed at enhancing sustainable tourism development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To assess ESG indices in hotels in Uzbekistan, three prestigious hotels were selected.

1. InterContinental Tashkent

Located in the heart of Tashkent, the InterContinental Tashkent hotel provides guests with a high level of service by combining luxury, modern amenities, and advanced technologies with sustainability principles. As one of the prominent hotels within an international chain, it organizes its operations in accordance with advanced standards of ESG—Environmental, Social, and Governance—indices.

InterContinental Tashkent pays particular attention to environmental efficiency starting from the architectural design of the building. The hotel is equipped with energy-efficient systems, modern insulation solutions, and technologies that ensure water-efficient consumption. A waste sorting and recycling system has been implemented in the building, and priority is given to the use of local and environmentally friendly products in restaurants and bars.

The high-floor restaurant and the open seasonal bar were constructed in a way that does not disrupt the city's ecological landscape, providing guests with the opportunity to relax without causing harm to the environment. All lighting systems are based on LED technology, thereby reducing the carbon footprint.

The professional development of hotel staff and the support of guests' health are key pillars of the social strategy. InterContinental Tashkent ensures maximum comfort through 40 elegant luxury suites, modern spacious guest rooms, and an exclusive executive lounge.

The restaurant and lounge areas offer healthy dining options, allergen-free menus, and a selection of local cuisine. Employees regularly participate in training programs, and working conditions are provided in accordance with international standards. The hotel's central facility—the Equilibrium Wellness Club—covers an area of 2,500 m² and features a 30-meter swimming pool, a fitness center, and services that promote a healthy lifestyle, offering guests a high-quality leisure experience.

The transparent governance system characteristic of the InterContinental brand has been fully implemented at its Tashkent property as well. Service processes are strictly monitored in accordance with established standards, guests' personal data are securely protected, and safety protocols are implemented at the level of international requirements. The hotel applies an innovative approach across all services: digitalized services, fast ordering through mobile applications, and smart room technologies enhance overall management efficiency.

2. Wyndham Garden Zomin — Winner of the “Best Eco-Hotel” Nomination

Located amid the unique natural surroundings of Zomin National Park, Wyndham Garden Zomin is not only a comfortable leisure destination but also a modern tourism facility that adheres to the principles of sustainable development. The hotel distinguishes itself by organizing its operations in alignment with ESG indices—Environmental, Social, and Governance criteria.

Wyndham Garden Zomin prioritizes environmental responsibility as a key focus area. Situated in a mountainous region, the hotel strives to minimize its impact on the surrounding environment. LED lighting systems, energy-efficient heating, and cooling equipment are used throughout the property. An electric vehicle charging station installed on the hotel premises promotes green transportation. The preservation

and landscaping of the garden area are carried out on a regular basis, with a landscape approach that is compatible with the natural ecosystem. In daily operations, the optimization of water and energy consumption also contributes to improving environmental performance.

The hotel places great emphasis on ensuring social well-being. Safe, comfortable, and fair working conditions are provided for employees, and their skills are regularly enhanced through training programs. A 24/7 reception service, guest safety measures, clean air, healthy dining options, and family-friendly infrastructure—all of these contribute to supporting the health and well-being of guests. To promote the development of the local community, the hotel has implemented initiatives such as using products from local producers and supporting them.

Wyndham Garden Zomin has organized its governance system according to international standards, with transparency and honesty in guest interactions being of paramount importance. Safety standards are strictly followed, and guests' personal data are reliably protected. Service processes undergo regular monitoring and are continuously improved in accordance with international quality management standards. Special areas designated for events and corporate meetings also reflect the high level of professional management and service culture.

3. Silk Road Samarkand Eco Village

Built in harmony with nature and based on the principles of sustainable tourism, the Eco Village is a modern complex consisting of 14 individual villas, offering guests an exclusive experience that combines the comfort of private residences with environmental cleanliness. The complex stands out for fully organizing its operations in accordance with ESG—Environmental, Social, and Governance standards.

In the construction of the Eco Village, primary attention was given to using natural, renewable, and environmentally friendly materials. All villas are entirely built from timber, enhancing energy efficiency, maintaining the natural microclimate, and reducing the carbon footprint. Each villa features a nearby private pool, managed in compliance with ecological standards.

The complex area is landscaped, with special attention given to preserving the natural environment. Technologies that optimize water and electricity consumption are applied, and a waste sorting and recycling system has been implemented.

Eco Village provides guests with independent living conditions reminiscent of home comfort. Each villa includes a kitchen, living room, and dining area, creating an ideal environment for family vacations, gatherings with friends, or small events. Comfortable working conditions are provided for staff, who receive regular training, and supporting local employment is one of the top priorities. Creating a safe, peaceful, and healthy environment for guests forms the foundation of the hotel's social responsibility.

The management system of Eco Village is designed in accordance with environmental and social principles. Service quality is regularly monitored, and communication with guests is open and transparent. All stages—from the reservation process to safety and service standards—are managed according to international requirements. The complex’s sustainable development strategy is aimed at maintaining long-term ecological and economic efficiency.

Comparison Table of Hotel ESG Indices

1. Environmental Comparison

Hotel	Strengths	Weaknesses	Rating (1–5)
InterContinental Tashkent	- Energy-efficient systems- LED lighting- Eco-friendly menu	- Limited information on green energy- Far from natural landscape	4
Wyndham Garden Zomin	- Located in a natural area- EV charging available- Resource-saving practices	- Limited information on waste management- No ecosystem monitoring	4
Eco Village	- Timber construction- Low carbon footprint- Natural landscape preserved	- Timber source unspecified- High water consumption (pools)	5

2. Social Comparison

Hotel	Strengths	Weaknesses	Rating (1–5)
InterContinental Tashkent	- Staff training- Wellness Club- High safety standards	- Community engagement not demonstrated	5
Wyndham Garden Zomin	- Family-friendly environment- Good working conditions for staff	- No information on professional development programs	4
Eco Village	- Independent living- Supports local employment	- Not adapted for people with disabilities- Safety protocols not specified	3

3. Governance Comparison

Hotel	Strengths	Weaknesses	Rating (1–5)
InterContinental Tashkent	- International standards- Strong data protection	- ESG reports not publicly available	5
Wyndham Garden Zomin	- Tourism-oriented governance	- No formal ESG policy- Limited innovative management systems	4
Eco Village	- Small complex — easier transparent management	- No certification- Safety standards not specified	2

The results show that ESG performance varies significantly across the selected hotels. Eco Village achieves the highest environmental score due to its low-carbon construction and integration with the natural landscape, despite weaknesses in water use and certification. InterContinental Tashkent demonstrates the strongest social and governance performance, supported by international management standards, staff training, and data protection systems. Wyndham Garden Zomin shows balanced but moderate results across all ESG dimensions, with environmental and social initiatives in place but limited formal governance and monitoring mechanisms. Overall, international hotel chains perform better in governance and social criteria, while eco-oriented projects lead in environmental sustainability, indicating the need for more integrated ESG implementation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of this comparison indicate that InterContinental Tashkent has a well-developed infrastructure in terms of environmental and social aspects, particularly standing out for energy-efficient technologies, staff training, and international management standards. However, the lack of publicly available ESG reports remains its main drawback.

Wyndham Garden Zomin is positively evaluated for its location in a natural area, resource-saving practices, and the creation of a family-friendly social environment. However, the lack of waste management, ecosystem monitoring, and formal ESG policies limits its development potential.

Eco Village receives the highest rating in terms of environmental sustainability, distinguished by its low carbon footprint and preservation of the natural landscape. Nevertheless, high water consumption and the absence of certification were identified as problematic areas. In terms of social criteria, InterContinental leads, whereas Eco Village does not sufficiently address inclusivity and safety issues. Regarding governance, large hotels have more stable systems, while smaller projects, despite transparency, lack standardization.

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